

netWorked Youth Research for **Empowerment** in the Digital society

Grant Agreement number: 727066

WYRED Research Cycle Infographic

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1 Introduction

WYRED (netWorked Youth Research for Empowerment in the Digital society) (García-Peñalvo, 2016; García-Peñalvo & Durán-Escudero, 2017; García-Peñalvo & Kearney, 2016) is a H2020 project that aims to provide a framework for research in which children and young people can express and explore their perspectives and interests in relation to digital society, but also a platform from which they can communicate their perspectives to other stakeholders effectively through innovative engagement processes.

This infographic summarizes the basic scheme of the a WYRED research cycle from the point of view of both Partners and Participants (Stakeholders), presenting the main comprised activities in each cycle stage.

2 Infographic

The image file of this infographic is available at <https://repositorio.grial.eu/handle/grial/839> or directly at https://repositorio.grial.eu/bitstream/grial/839/1/WYRED_WP1_D1.1_1stcycle-01.png.

3 Citation

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4 References

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